

Mean tungro disease incidence (□), infection with rice tungro bacilliform (▨) and spherical (■) viruses, and number of green leafhoppers (▩) per 10 sweeps of a 30-cm-diameter insect net in advanced breeding lines and varieties at six locations in India, Indonesia, and the Philippines in replicated field trials in 1995 and 1996.

Pest resistance

Advanced breeding lines with resistance to rice tungro viruses

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Some 139 advanced breeding lines with improved agronomic characters derived from crosses involving tungro-resistant rice varieties were evaluated for resistance to rice tungro viruses under greenhouse conditions. These lines consistently showed a resistant reaction to tungro under natural field infection in the tungro nursery at IRRI for at least six growing seasons. In the crosses, Utri Rajapan, Utri Merah, ARC11554,

Habiganj DW8, and wild rices *Oryza longistaminata* and *O. rufipogon* (accession no. 105908 and 105910 and one with an unknown accession no.) were used as sources of resistance to tungro, whereas IR1561-228-3-3, IR24, and IR64 were used as the recurrent parents. Except for ARC11554, *O. longistaminata*, IR24, and IR64, all the other parents are susceptible to the virus vector green leafhopper (GLH).

The breeding lines were tested for tungro reaction using the forced-inoculation method. Some or 30-40 seven-day-old seedlings of each breeding line were inoculated with the virus for 24 h in test tubes using three viruliferous GLH, *Nepho-tettix virescens* (Distant), fed for 4 d on plants infected with rice tungro bacilli-form virus (RTBV) and

rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). After inoculation, the seedlings were planted in clay pots at 10 seedlings pot⁻¹ and maintained for 1 mo inside insect-proof enclosures in the greenhouse. Leaf samples were collected from each plant and tested by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). In the 1995 dry-season test, inoculated seedlings of the test lines were transplanted in the field after leaf sampling to further subject the materials to natural infection. Each of the lines was planted in 2 rows of inoculated seedlings, with 20 hills row⁻¹. One month after transplanting, leaf samples were again collected from each plant and tested by ELISA.

Only 94 of the breeding lines tested were confirmed to have resistance to tungro. Of these, 4 showed resistance to both RTBV and RTSV, whereas the other 90 breeding lines showed resistance to RTSV only (Table 1). Two breeding lines each from the crosses involving *O. rufipogon* (accession no. 105910) and Habiganj DW8 were resistant to both RTBV and RTSV, whereas breeding lines derived from crosses involving the other parents showed resistance to RTSV only. Progenies of *O. rufipogon*, Utri Merah, and Utri Rajapan were among the lines that exhibited a high level of resistance to RTSV.

An increase in RTBV and RTSV infection was observed in most of the breeding lines when inoculated seedlings of the test materials were transplanted in the field and further exposed to natural infection (Table 2). Breeding lines from Utri Merah and Utri Rajapan crosses, however, showed a decrease in RTBV infection even after further exposure to natural infection. Utri Merah is known to have resistance to the multiplication of RTBV and the decrease in RTBV detected in these breeding lines is presumed to be due to a decrease in virus titre in the infected plants.

Some of the most promising breeding lines from the crosses tested in these trials were selected for further evaluation in areas with high tungro incidence. These breeding lines are now being tested in replicated field trials in India, Indonesia, and the Philippines. ■

Table 1. Average percentage infection of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in advanced breeding lines with different sources of resistance.

Cross	Resistant lines (no.)	Infection ^a (%)				
		BS	B	S	BB	SS
<i>1995 dry season^b</i>						
IR1561-228-3-3*3/ <i>O. longistaminata</i>	16	8.3	57.2	2.0	65.5	10.3
IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Rajapan	15	14.8	72.7	0.2	87.5	15.0
IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Merah	10	8.6	56.1	2.1	64.7	10.7
IR1561-2128-3-3*4/Utri Merah	10	5.7	53.1	1.7	58.8	7.4
IR1561-228-3-3*6/ARC11554	5	5.0	50.0	1.6	55.0	6.6
IR1561-228-3-3*4/Habiganj DW8	2	1.5	15.5	1.5	17.0	3.0
IR1561-228-3-3*6/Habiganj DW8	2	6.0	61.5	0.0	67.5	6.0
<i>1996 wet season</i>						
IR1561-228-3-3*2/ <i>O. longistaminata</i>	2	1.5	69.0	1.5	70.5	3.0
IR1561-228-3-3*3/ <i>O. longistaminata</i> ^c	2	1.5	71.5	1.5	73.0	3.0
IR1561-228-3-3*2/ <i>O. longistaminata</i> //IR24	2	1.5	82.5	0.0	84.0	1.5
IR1561-228-3-3*4/ <i>O. longistaminata</i> //3*IR24	4	1.5	59.0	0.0	60.5	1.5
IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Merah ^c	3	1.0	30.0	0.0	31.0	1.0
IR1561-228-3-3*4/Utri Merah ^c	2	0.0	40.5	0.0	40.5	0.0
IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Merah//IR24	3	9.0	48.3	0.0	57.3	9.0
IR1561-228-3-3*6/ARC 11554 ^c	5	2.4	43.6	0.6	46.0	3.0
IR1561-228-3-3*3/Habiganj DW8	1	3.0	47.0	0.0	50.0	3.0
IR1561-228-3-3*4/Habiganj DW8 ^c	2	4.0	24.5	4.5	28.5	8.5
IR1561-228-3-3*6/Habiganj DW8	1	9.0	53.0	0.0	62.0	9.0
IR1561-228-3-3*3/Habiganj DW8//4*IR64	5	3.0	39.8	0.0	42.8	3.0
IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Rajapan ^c	2	5.0	77.5	0.0	82.5	5.0
IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Rajapan//IR24	3	1.0	68.7	0.0	69.7	1.0
IR1561-228-3-3/ <i>O. rufipogon</i> (Acc. 105910)	1	0.0	76.0	0.0	76.0	0.0
IR1561-228-3-3/ <i>O. rufipogon</i> (Acc. 105908)//IR24	5	0.0	69.4	0.0	69.4	0.0
IR24/ <i>O. rufopogon</i> (Acc. 105910)//3*IR64	2	0.0	26.0	0.0	26.0	0.0
IR1561-228-3-3//IR42/ <i>O. rufipogon</i> (unknown Acc. no.)	5	0.0	60.2	0.8	60.2	0.8

^aAv of resistant lines. Infection of tungro viruses was assessed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. BS = RTBV + RTSV, B = RTBV alone, S = RTSV alone, BB = total RTBV (BS + B), SS = total RTSV (BS + S). ^bTwo inoculation trials conducted. Percentage infection is av of two trials. ^cAdvanced progenies of breeding lines identified as resistant in 1995 dry season trial.

Table 2. Average percentage infection of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in advanced breeding lines inoculated in the greenhouse and subjected to natural infection in the field.

Cross	Lines tested ^a (no.)	Infection (%) ^b				
		BS	B	S	BB	SS
IR1561-228-3-3*3/ <i>O. longistaminata</i>	4	18.8 (4.6)	55.3 (68.4)	2.8 (0.5)	74.1 (73.0)	21.6 (5.1)
IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Rajapan	4	32.6 (20.3)	52.8 (71.4)	4.5 (0.1)	85.4 (91.7)	37.1 (20.4)
IR1561-228-3-3*2/Utri Merah	4	5.7 (4.3)	43.0 (71.8)	3.2 (0.6)	48.7 (76.1)	8.9 (4.9)
IR1561-228-3-3*6/ARC11554	4	8.8 (2.8)	64.0 (59.2)	1.8 (0)	72.8 (62.0)	10.6 (2.8)
IR1561-228-3-3*6/Habiganj DW8	4	9.2 (5.0)	59.8 (47.4)	1.6 (0)	69.0 (52.4)	10.8 (5.0)

^aTest lines were inoculated with RTBV + RTSV in the greenhouse at 7d after sowing (DAS) and transplanted in the field at 38 DAS. Values represent infection with tungro viruses at 69 DAS. Values in parentheses represent infection with tungro viruses at 38 DAS. ^bInfection of tungro viruses was assessed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. BS = RTBV + RTSV, B = RTBV alone, S = RTSV alone, BB = total RTBV (BS + B), SS = total RTSV (BS + S).

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

Stress tolerance — adverse soils

Seasonal differences in iron toxicity tolerance of lowland rice cultivars

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Iron toxicity is a major stress and yield-reducing factor in irrigated and rainfed lowlands in West Africa. Varietal tolerance is the most practical and cost-effective means of reducing iron toxicity in iron-toxic soils. We have been evaluating lowland rice cultivars for iron toxicity tolerance at Korhogo, Côte d'Ivoire, a site with a consistent and high iron toxicity pressure on plants. Because irrigation water is available, it was possible to evaluate germplasm in both the wet and dry seasons.

We have observed that iron toxicity pressure is higher in the dry season than in the wet season at Korhogo. In the 1994 wet season (Jul-Nov 1994) and 1995 dry season (Dec 1994-Apr 1995), we evaluated the performance of 12 elite selections (based on evaluations made in 1992 and 1993). To determine the yield potential of these cultivars, they were also grown at Mbe, which provides a lower level of stress.

Experiments at both sites used a randomized complete block design with four replications. The plot size was 12 m² at Mbe and 24 m² at Korhogo. All plots received 20-36-36 kg NPK ha⁻¹ as a basal application. A total of 80 kg N ha⁻¹ was added to each plot. The soil at Mbe was an Alfisol (pH 6.2; organic carbon, 1.8%; extractable Fe, 93 mg kg⁻¹) with sandy clay-loam texture; the soil at Korhogo was an Ultisol (pH 5.7; organic carbon, 1.02%; extractable Fe, 154 mg kg⁻¹) with sandy loam texture.

The cultivars evaluated at Korhogo had large differences in yield during the wet and dry seasons (see table). Iron toxicity scores at Korhogo, based on bronzing symptoms on the rice plant